

Development of an AI ML platform for critical metals exploration: a review and future roadmap

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Abstract

This work presents a review and a new concept for the development and deployment of an AI ML platform for critical metals exploration. The proposed platform aims to integrate structural, petrological, mineralogical, stratigraphic, geophysical, geochemical, and geoinformatics data to generate insights into critical metals mineralization in a geological terrane, especially in the Archean-Proterozoic cratons. A cloud based big data platform is envisaged for storage, integration and processing of data. A next-gen visualization with UX/UI features is envisaged. The solution will accelerate the exploration and production lifecycle of critical metals, which are raw materials required for renewable energy generation. This solution will fast-track energy transition by enhancing the production of energy storage materials.

Keywords: machine learning; artificial intelligence; critical metals, energy transition; energy storage materials.

1. Introduction

Global warming and climate change are the two most imminent threats to the existence of mankind on Earth ([Zhao et al., 2022](#); [Abbass et al., 2022](#); [Hansen et al., 2025](#)). The exponential increase in the burning of fossil fuels has led to a surge in greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, resulting in enhanced heat retention by the atmosphere, which has been identified as the root cause of the warming of the atmosphere ([Liu et al., 2023](#)). Therefore, burning fossil fuels be reduced, and the carbon emission into the atmosphere must be decreased on a war footing to control global warming

(Choudhury et al., 2023). However, an increase in the global population in the last few decades (Gu et al, 2021) has led to an increase in energy demand, which is currently primarily met by the burning of fossil fuels. Therefore, there is an urgent need to switchover to clean and green energy (Ang et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2024) to escape the wrath of global warming. However, this transition requires abundant availability of critical metals such as Lithium, vanadium, chromium, copper, Thorium, etc., which are currently globally scarce commodities (Slowinski et al., 2013; Balaram and Santosh, 2025). There are legacy methods of exploration and production of critical metals with a long-life cycle and poor reliability. There are several techniques deployed by mineral exploration companies for discovery of critical metals from Earth's crust. Due to these techniques deployed in silos, there is an urgent need to integrate them, and generate high-end insights to locate subsurface critical metals deposits. With this overview, this work presents an AI ML-driven solution to locate subsurface critical metal deposits from an array of data generated by mineral exploration companies. This solution aims to enhance the success rates of the discovery of critical metal deposits. The solution leverages a big data platform, high-end processing unit, and next-gen UX-UI visualization features to generate recommendations for subsurface location of critical mineral resources.

2. Previous work

Several entities across the world are working to implement AI for mineral exploration. Companies such as Earth AI (<https://earth-ai.com/technology>), VRIFY (<https://vrify.com/>), and MINERS AI (<https://www.minersai.com/>) are some of the prominent AI companies working to deploy AI and ML in mineral exploration. In the last few years, several workers published works highlighting the progress in the implementation of AI and ML in mineral exploration. Fu et al. (2025) discussed in detail the evolution of ML in large-scale mineral prospectivity prediction from 2016 to 2025. Yang et al (2024) presented a review of AI implementation in mineral exploration. They outlined the

need for the development of AI models that couple geological knowledge with mineral exploration data. [Alabi et al \(2025\)](#) outlined the need for AI and ML in mineral prospecting, ore reserve estimation, and geochemical anomaly detection. [Zuo et al \(2024\)](#) suggested that AI algorithms are critical for identifying nonlinear mineralization patterns in large volumes of data obtained from mineral exploration. [Hoseinzade and Bazoobandi \(2024\)](#) used deep embedded clustering to delineate multivariate geochemical anomalies associated with mineral deposits. [Nasreddine et al \(2024\)](#) applied ML models to predict rare earth elements (REE) distribution in Tethyan phosphate ore deposits. [Davies et al \(2025\)](#) highlighted that low success rates in the discovery of critical mineral deposits are primarily due to limited interdisciplinary collaboration, poor data quality, inconsistent sampling, and the complexity of geoscientific problems. Insights obtained by previous workers suggests that there is an urgent need to upscale efforts to develop AI ML driven robust and reliable mineral exploration platforms.

3. System architecture

We propose a system architecture of an AI ML driven mineral exploration solution that leverages a big data platform and ML algorithms to generate insights to locate subsurface critical mineral deposits. The high-level architecture of solution is given in [Fig. 1](#). The big data platforms such as Hadoop, Cassandra, and MongoDB should be evaluated for their utility in mineral exploration. The solution will leverage cloud-based secure big data services such as Azure, AWS, and Google AI platforms for data integration, ML modelling, and running data analytics. The open-source data of geological terranes obtained from Google Maps, Google Earth, and the USGS data repository will be leveraged to obtain the location, topography, and geological features of the terrane. The digital elevation map (DEM) generated from USGS data will help generate the topography of the area of interest. Satellite hyperspectral infrared imagery will help delineate hydrothermal

alteration, leaching, and mineralization zones such as those associated with porphyry copper deposits. Python libraries will be leveraged for programming the algorithms on Visual Studio. Visualization platforms such as Tableau, Looker Studio by Google, Power BI, and Zoho will be used for data visualization.

Fig.1. System architecture of an integrated platform for critical metal exploration.

4. Solution overview

The solution will have several layers, with the recommendation layer being the solution output (Fig. 1 and 2). The visualization and recommendation layers will contain outcomes of the solution. The Google map layer forms the foundation to which all other layers are tagged. The ArcGIS layer will generate a DEM and identify high-level mineralization zones. The geophysical and geochemical layers will be manual data entry layers, whereas data integration and AI ML layers will be algorithm layers. Python libraries will be used to generate code and develop these layers. The visualization and recommendation layers will display layers, highlighting probable

mineralization zones that require intensive exploration. High end UX UI with 3D animations will simulate a subsurface critical metal deposit. The animation will show subsurface lithologies, their thicknesses, density, folds, faults, fractures, other structures, and the probable location of mineralization.

Fig. 2. A stacked model of the MINEX AI solution.

6. Solution Modules

The solution will store the data generated during different types of exploration carried out in the terrane. The suggested modules are

- a. **Literature module:** This module will be a repository of all previous information on the terrane obtained from abstracts of the research papers published in reputed journals and scholarly articles (Fig. 3). The data and text mining tools will be leveraged to generate this repository.

Fig. 3. A flow chart illustrating the literature survey module

- b. **ArcGIS Module:** This module will consist of satellite imagery, a DEM of the terrane, a geological structural map, and lithology data. This module will also highlight alteration zones from hyperspectral images.
- c. **Geophysical Module:** The mineral deposits generate a fingerprint of geophysical data, which helps identify their subsurface location. Some mineral deposits have density anomalies, while others have magnetic anomalies. Some deposits have high radiation density, whereas others have distinct electrical properties. Such properties are captured during geophysical survey and exploration, and the data is captured in subsurface three dimensions. This geophysical data of a terrane will be imported into a Big Data platform and tagged w.r.t its Google map and ArcGIS location.
- d. **Geochemical Module:** Geochemical anomalies are associated with subsurface metal deposits. The geochemical analysis of surface and core samples helps identify such anomalies. Mineralogical and geochemical study of the terrane generates geochemical data. The

petrographic study of the rock generates mineralogy data. The chemical composition of minerals is obtained from an electron probe microanalyzer (EPMA) and laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA ICPMS). The whole rock chemical composition of the rock is obtained by x-ray fluorescence (XRF) and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP MS). The geochemical data will be imported into the big data platform and integrated with the Google map, ArcGIS and field data of the terrane.

- e. **Stratigraphy module:** This module will be updated with chronostratigraphic data of the terrane. The ages of the rocks will be defined in this module.

7. AI ML Algorithms

The ML models work on the basic tenet of problem identification, data collection, data processing, massaging and cleansing, identifying an ML model to deploy, and training and testing of the ML model (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. A flow chart illustrating a generic ML deployment model.

Before coding, flowcharts will be generated to illustrate the logic of the solution. The flow charts will be developed taking into consideration different factors that lead to mineralization in a terrane. For example, a sample flow chart for recommending geochemical analysis of a basalt sample for base metal exploration in the Precambrian terrane is given in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. A flow chart illustrating steps to get a recommendation for geochemical analysis

8. Discussion and conclusion

Our work gives a concept for the development and deployment of an AI ML solution for critical metals exploration. This solution will be a next-gen deep tech digital platform to facilitate and fast-track critical metals exploration. It will be an integrated platform, which can be customized for a geological terrane with the help of existing geological, remote sensing, geophysical, and geochemical data. Python will be used for algorithm code generation. Big Data platforms will be used for the storage of datasets. Algorithms will be written to integrate data. Algorithms will be coded to generate relevant information from integrated data. The prospect insights will be generated by the integration of different datasets. Descriptive, prescriptive, and predictive analytics will be used to understand the patterns from data. Supervised and unsupervised machine learning models will be applied to datasets. The NextGen 3D visualization dashboards will display

the location of mineralization. A recommendation dashboard will give insights into mineralization.

Acknowledgements

The author thanks UPES Dehradun for providing permission to publish this work. The thought leadership for this work is supported by PTRE TRANS AI, a deeptech start-up company incubated at UPES, Dehradun. No external funding was obtained to carry out this work.

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